

ETYMOLOGICAL FEATURES OF PHRASEOLOGICAL EXPRESSIONS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the etymological aspect of the linguoculturological analysis of phraseological units as a means of identifying the features of the national mentality. The object of this observation is to determine ways to replenish the phraseological fund of the English language on the basis of phraseological units.

Keywords: phraseological unit, etymology, linguistic and cultural analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The etymological approach in the study of vocabulary and phraseology of a language provides rich material for studying the linguocultural features of a particular language community. The connection between phraseology and cultural and national traditions has been proved. However, in order to obtain objective data regarding national consciousness through the prism of phraseology, an etymological analysis of phraseological units is necessary to confirm their ethnic linguistic affiliation.

The object of research in this article is phraseological units (PU) of the English language, belonging to the phraseological-semantic field "Labor activity" and being a means of interpreting cultural and symbolic representations inherent in the everyday mentality of a native speaker⁸⁴. The subject of the study is the indicated phraseological units, considered through the prism of etymological analysis from the point of view of their cultural and symbolic semantic experience that is preserved/modified in them.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Recently, many works have been written on phraseology in linguistic and cultural terms. A.P. Vasilenko offers a functional-parametric description of the semantics of phraseological units in the study of the phraseology of a language. This technique includes, among other things, a detailed study of the linguoculturological parameter of the semantics of phraseological units as "a way of ethnic commentary on the internal form, because it is in the figurative basis that the national vision of the surrounding

⁸⁴ Vasilenko A.P. Aspects of the semantics of phraseological units (based on the Russian and French languages): Dis. ... Dr. Philol. Sciences. M., 2011.

reality is contained, represented by a stable unit and called the phraseological picture of the world.”⁸⁵

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The transfer of the meaning of terminological combinations provides us with a living example associated with the histories of medieval England. To prevent cases of burial of living people, a thread was attached to the hand of the deceased, which went out and was attached to the bell. A “dead person” who woke up could attract the attention of a person who was specially hired to listen to the bells in the cemetery at night. This is how the expression "the graveyard shift" appeared, and later it became a general designation for any work on the night shift from midnight to eight in the morning.

The next way of forming phraseological units, which occurs quite often, is the change in the meaning of free phrases. Words that previously had free use move into the category of set expressions and, losing their motivation, acquire a different meaning. For example, the stable expression "bring home the bacon" in modern English means "to earn a living". Let us trace the etymology of the above phraseological unit by referring to the historical conditions of peasant life in medieval England. Meat (bacon) was an attribute of security, and if it was possible to get it, it was a source of pride. Bacon was hung on a hook in a conspicuous place so that guests could see the prosperity of the family.

Metaphor as a linguistic means is often found in the formation of phraseological units-somatisms and phraseological units-zoonyms. Phraseologism "elbow grease" means diligent manual labor: "You need to use some elbow grease". Phraseologism has a playful meaning, which consists in the fact that in order to achieve success in some activities, special efforts must be made. The word "grease" alludes to the use of grease for the mechanisms to make work easier.

Phraseological-semantic field "labor activity" contains a group of phraseological units-zoonyms. One of the semantic characteristics of this group is its expressiveness, where the connotative coloring of a phraseological unit appears as one of its functions. All zoomorphisms are the result of a metaphorical rethinking of the properties of an animal in comparison with the human sphere of activity⁸⁶.

“The combination of nominative and emotional-evaluative elements in the content of phraseological units allows native speakers to use phraseological units to

⁸⁵ Leskina S.V. Russian and English phraseological units of pejorative semantics as a reflection of the language picture of the world: Monograph. Chelyabinsk, 2019.

⁸⁶ Seidl J., McMordie W. English Idioms and how to Use Them. Oxford University Press, 2018.

convey not only the logical content of a thought, but also a figurative idea of something, and through the latter to express an emotional expression to the subject of thought”.

For example, the expression "to work like a dog" is formed using a figurative metaphor. This phraseological unit with a zoonym component, it can be assumed, comes from the "Turnspit Dog", a special breed of dog bred to turn mill wheels. This breed is mentioned in William Bingley's *Memoirs of British Quadrupeds* (1809) under the name "Turnspete".

The expressiveness of these phraseological units can be represented in various language ways, including the use of metaphor, comparisons, alliteration. V.N. Vokurov, considering these means of linguistic expressiveness involved in the formation of the expressiveness of a phraseological unit, identifies "qualitative, quantitative and qualitative-quantitative expressive units".

In quantitative phraseological units, a high degree of manifestation of the attribute of denotation is emphasized: "to work like a racing dog".

The meanings of qualitative phraseological units are formed with the help of additional semantic nuances based on the features of the used image. Basically, this group consists of comparative words such as "as busy as a bee; work like a horse".

The connotation of qualitative-quantitative phraseological units is made up of this intensity of action and a high degree of manifestation of an attribute of an object or action: "horse and foot" (with all one's strength, with all one's strength), "hammer and tongs" (to work together)⁸⁷.

Exploring this phraseological-semantic field and considering the term "phraseology" in a broad sense, we also include phraseological units with the structure of a simple and complex sentence (proverbs and sayings). Some of them are built on the basis of unrealistic associative images (A cat in gloves catches no mice), others use images of everyday life (Quick at meat, quick at work). But the vast majority of proverbs of the English language related to labor activity are of a moralizing nature, which is 24% of all selected phraseological units in this area.

CONCLUSION

The study of the phraseological layer of any language allows us to solve two problems at once. First, by studying it as a fact of the modern literary language, we learn to think in terms of images of a native speaker of the language being studied. The use of phraseological units in the speech of an Englishman is a completely natural phenomenon. A native speaker of English sometimes uses a lexical unit without

⁸⁷ Sherwood-tavern. Literary and historical forum. URL: <http://forum.sherwood-tavern.net/viewtopic.php?id=> (accessed 12/15/2013).

thinking about using a phraseological phrase in his speech. It is believed that the idiomatic baggage of a cultural native speaker is at least 5000 expressions.

Secondly, by studying phraseology as a reflection of national realities, we comprehend the uniqueness of the culture of the people. "Linguistic and cultural commentary of phraseological units allows us to see the hidden, not self-evident features of the embodiment of cultural entities in phraseological units." The ethno-cultural value of a phraseological unit can be revealed by identifying the cultural meanings embedded in the semantics of phraseological unit, i.e. myths (mythologemes), archetypes, rituals, stereotypes, beliefs, customs, standards, etc. signs of the national culture of the people. Cultural meanings are contained in the internal form of phraseological units, which is a figurative basis for the formation of phraseological units of the language.

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